

MODE III INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE OF TOUGHENED RESIN COMPOSITES

Steven L. Donaldson
Materials Laboratory
Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories
Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio 45433 USA

Shankar Mall
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Air Force Institute of Technology
Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio 45433 USA

INTRODUCTION

Laminates of advanced fiber-reinforced composite materials constructed by the stacking of unidirectional plies may experience out-of-plane stresses from many sources, including the anisotropic mismatch between layers (especially near free-edges), discontinuities such as ply terminations, and direct out-of-plane loading such as transverse impact from runway debris, hail, and dropped tools. Since, in typical aerospace structural composites, there is no reinforcement in the out-of-plane direction, the out-of-plane stresses may give rise to failure in the matrix between the plies. Failure of this type, commonly referred to as delamination, is generally not considered to be a primary failure mode, but its presence can be responsible for subsequent primary failure, such as the significant reduction in laminate compression strength due to the presence of delamination.

Delamination can propagate under any one of, or more likely a combination of, the three fracture modes (Mode I peeling, Mode II forward shearing, and Mode III out-of-plane tearing). A complex combination of these crack-tip modes can be present even when the laminate is subjected to global in-plane loading only. Test methods for the characterization of Mode I, II, and mixed Modes I-II interlaminar fracture toughness are becoming fairly well developed. Several test methods to measure the Mode III interlaminar fracture toughness have been proposed [1,2]. This paper presents the results, using the test method presented in [1], of tests conducted to measure the Mode III interlaminar fracture toughness of several toughened resin composite systems.

Because of the brittle nature of current epoxy systems, several approaches to increase the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite materials are receiving attention. One approach is the mechanical addition of transverse reinforcement by stitching fibers through the laminate before curing. Another technique is to add thin layers of tough adhesive between ply layers while laying-up the laminate. Increasing the inter-ply thickness of the existing matrix may lead to increased toughness. The last two methods involve changing the matrix, in one case by using a ductile matrix thermoplastic. The final approach is to toughen the brittle resin by modifying it. The toughening of existing brittle systems leads to composites which are generally not as tough as those with thermoplastic matrices, however, they retain the processing methods and certain other properties of their forerunners. These can be advantageous in some cases. Materials modified by toughening existing brittle systems were examined in this study.

MATERIALS

Three carbon-fiber reinforced 177° C cure toughened resin composites were arbitrarily chosen for this study. The three materials tested were Ciba-Geigy T40/R6376 modified epoxy-based resin, Hercules IM7/8552 toughened matrix, and BASF Narmco T800 (T40)/5245C modified bismaleimide resin. Data from a brittle epoxy matrix composite, Hercules AS4/3502 will also be presented to serve as a reference. All systems were cured according to the manufacturer's instructions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The details of the split cantilever beam test used for this study are presented in [1]. Briefly, as shown in Figure 1, the test specimens consisted of 3 mm thick by 12.7 mm width by 280 mm length strips of laminate adhesively bonded (Hysol 9309.3NA was used in this study) between aluminum support bars. At the end of each specimen, the laminate strip contained a 30 mm Kapton implant at the midplane. This implant starter crack was manually extended, using a razor blade, just prior to testing to a typical length of 60 mm from the specimen end (35 mm from the load axis). The edges of the laminates were painted with white typewriter correction fluid to monitor crack length. The ends of the bars were then loaded in a servohydraulic test machine to produce the out-of-plane tearing. Note that the support bars were bolted to splice plates which were, in turn, bolted to center blocks. The total fixture forced the load axis and the crack to be coincident. All of the fixture components were designed to be very stiff, with respect to the laminate, to minimize specimen twisting.

The specimens were loaded at a constant displacement rate of 0.25 mm/min. All testing was conducted under room temperature laboratory conditions. The specimens had been stored in a dessicator cabinet between fabrication and testing to eliminate possible moisture effects. Load and end displacement were recorded on an x-y recorder during the test. Crack length was monitored visually with a magnifier and crack lengths were immediately marked on the x-y recorder output. Typical load versus displacement plots for the three systems are given in Figure 2. Stable crack growth was achieved (with the exception of the several jumps seen in Figure 2) in the toughened systems, similar to that observed in the brittle matrix systems. The difference in the initial compliance and maximum load for the four systems does not indicate the material toughness, but is a function of the starter crack length and toughness. For clarity, the crack length measurements have been omitted from Figure 2.

DATA REDUCTION

The first data reduction technique considered was the area method [3], which states that the change in area in the P vs δ curve is the energy lost due to the crack extension. The equation for this is:

$$G_{IIIc,i} = \{P_i(d\delta/da)_i - \delta_i(dP/da)_i\}/(2b)$$

where G_{IIIc} is the Mode III critical interlaminar fracture toughness, P_i , δ_i , and a_i are the current end load, end displacement, and crack length. The value of b , the width of the crack, was 12.7 mm throughout this study. In addition, $d\delta/da$ and dP/da are the displacement and load changes from the i to the $i+1$ data. Typically, 16-18 readings were taken per specimen.

The second method used was an empirical compliance calibration method [4]. The equation used is:

$$G_{IIIc,i} = nP_i\delta_i/(2ba_i)$$

The value n is the compliance curve-fit parameter, determined experimentally for each test specimen. The compliance calibration for the split cantilever beam specimen is discussed in detail in [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Mode III critical interlaminar fracture toughness results are presented in Table 1 and Figure 3. Average values and standard deviation are shown. The G_{IIIc} for the toughened systems showed a greater scatter as a function of crack length than that seen in the brittle resin composite [1]. There was no indication, however, of any trends in toughness versus crack length, as is often observed when fiber bridging dominates the measured toughness (toughness appears to increase as the crack extends, until often a plateau is reached). Toughness values were first averaged over the length of each specimen; these values were then averaged for the three specimens of each material. As with the brittle 3502 resin results [1], the area and compliance data reduction methods were in close agreement, as shown in Figure 3.

A comparison of the results with the AS4/3502 brittle epoxy resin composite and the Mode I toughness value for each material is given in Table 1. The results show that the Mode III toughness values are 40% higher for the R6376 matrix composite, 81% higher for the 8552 matrix composite, and 34% higher for the 5245C matrix composite when compared to the AS4/3502. Thus, as in the Mode I case, the toughening of the matrix increased the composite Mode III toughness. Further, the G_{IIIc} values are considerably larger than the G_{Ic} values for the toughened composite systems as in the case of the brittle system. The situation is actually more complex than a direct comparison can provide, due to

the differences in fibers and possible fiber sizing effects. In addition, the 5245C should be compared to an untoughened BMI. Finally, the variability in materials, test techniques, and difficulties with fiber bridging in the Mode I tests should be kept in mind when comparing the results provided in Tables 1 and 2.

The 8552 system had the greatest tendency of the three systems to exhibit debonding, stick-slip, and fiber bridging behavior. In addition, it had the roughest fracture surface on visual examination. Note that, in agreement with these observations is the fact that the 8552 system had the highest measured toughness.

FRACTOGRAPHY

Fracture surface features obtained using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) are presented in Figure 4. Due to space limitations, only the T40/R6376 surfaces are presented. Part (a) is a fractograph of the Mode I area of the surface, formed during the razor pre-cracking technique. Part (b) is a view of the surface created during the Mode III tearing. The Mode I surface is notably different from the AS4/3502 brittle resin Mode I surface. The R6376 surface has a much rougher texture, not the smooth brittle cleavage texture seen in the brittle resin. Table 1 indicates the more than two-fold increase in G_{Ic} over the brittle resin AS4/3502. The Mode III surface, unlike the Mode I surface just discussed, appears fairly similar to the corresponding surface seen in the brittle 3502 [1]. Some evidence of ductility can be seen, primarily at the bottom of the figure.

CONCLUSIONS

The split cantilever beam test was successful in testing composites with intermediate toughness matrices, e.g., toughened epoxies and BMIs. Three 177° C curing systems were examined. Steady crack growth was observed in all three systems under constant displacement rate testing. The systems produced Mode III toughness results which were 34-81% higher than the reference brittle epoxy system. Fracture surface examination revealed that the surfaces of the toughened systems showed more embrittlement under the Mode III loading than in the Mode I case.

REFERENCES

1. Donaldson, S. L., "Mode III Interlaminar Fracture Characterization of Composite Materials," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol 32, 1988, pp. 225-249.
2. Becht, G., and Gillespie, J. W., Jr., "Design and Analysis of the Crack Rail Shear Specimen for Mode III Interlaminar Fracture," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol 31, 1988, pp. 143-157.
3. Whitney, J. M., Browning, C. E., and Hoogsteden, W., "A Double Cantilever Beam Test for Characterizing Mode I Delamination of Composite Materials," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, October 1982, pp. 297-313.
4. Berry, J. P., "Determination of Fracture Surface Energies by the Cleavage Technique," *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol 34, No 1, January 1963, pp. 62-68.
5. Jordan, W. M. and Bradley, W. L., "Micromechanisms of Fracture in Toughened Graphite-Epoxy Laminates," *Toughened Composites*, ASTM STP 937, 1987, pp. 95-114.
6. Lee, S. M., "Compression-After-Impact of Composites with Toughened Matrices," *SAMPE Journal*, March/April 1986, pp. 64-68.
7. Davies, P. and de Charentenay, F. X., "The Effect of Temperature on the Interlaminar Fracture of Tough Composites," *Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Vol 3, 1987, pp. 3.284-3.295.
8. Hercules Aerospace Composite Products Group, unpublished data.
9. Shah, R. C., Miliziano, G., Viswanathan, A. V., "Interlaminar Fracture Characteristics of Tougher Thermoset Materials," *Journal of Aircraft*, Vol 23, No 7, July 1986, pp. 599-605.
10. Lee, S., Scott, R. F., Gaudert, P. C., Ubbink, W. H., and Poon, C., "Mechanical Testing of Toughened Resin Composite Materials," *Composites*, Vol 19, No 4, July 1988, pp. 300-310.
11. Mall, S., Yun, K.T., and Kochhar, N.K., "Characterization of Matrix Toughness Effect on Cyclic Delamination Growth in Graphite Fiber Composites," *Composite Materials*, ASTM STP 1012, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1988 (in press).

Material	G_{IIIc} , area meth. (kJ/m ²)	G_{Ic} (kJ/m ²)	$G_{Ic}/G_{Ic,3502}$	$G_{IIIc}/G_{IIIc,3502}$	G_{IIIc}/G_{Ic}
AS4/3502 (reference)	1.29±0.15	0.189 ¹	1	1	6.83
T40/R6376	1.81±0.14	0.420 ² 0.18-0.63 ⁴ 0.473 ⁸	2.22 0.95-3.33 2.5	1.40	4.31 2.87 3.83
IM7/8552	2.33±0.25	0.272 ⁵	1.44	1.81	8.57
T800/5245C (T40)	1.73±0.06	0.301 ⁶ 0.228 ⁷	1.59 1.21	1.34	5.75 7.59

1. Data from Jordan and Bradley [5].
2. Data from Lee [6] on AS6/R6376.
3. Data from Davies and de Charentenay [7] on IM6/6376.
4. Data from Davies and de Charentenay [7] on IM6/6376. Lower value is the initiation value based on an acoustic emission signal. Upper value represents fully developed fiber bridging.
5. Data from [8] on AS4/8552. Averaged over the length of W^TD^CB with fiber bridging.
6. Data from Shah, et. al. [9] on AS6/5245C. Lowest value taken from G_{Ic} vs crack length data, where fiber bridging effects are minimized.
7. Data from Lee, et. al. [10] on IM6/5245C. Authors' state fiber bridging resulted in artificially high values.
8. Data from Mall, et. al. [11] on IM6/R6376.

Table 1. Critical interlaminar strain energy release rates and a comparison for the brittle reference and three toughened systems. Literature values of Mode I data is also presented.

Figure 1. Photograph of the split cantilever beam test in progress.

Figure 2. Load versus specimen end displacement for the three toughened systems and one brittle resin reference system.

Figure 3. Mode III toughness results for the three toughened systems and one brittle resin reference system.

Figure 4. T40/R6376 fracture surfaces: (a) Mode I, (b) Mode III.